

Robust Exponential Complexity Growth in the Universe

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Abstract: The history of the universe can be understood as a continuous increase in complexity, from elementary particles to human civilization and technology. This article argues that this development is both robust and exponential: each step in complexity enables the conditions for the next, faster step. Catastrophic events such as mass extinctions or wars have not fundamentally altered this trajectory; on geological and cosmological scales, they appear irrelevant to the long-term trend. Although complexity is notoriously difficult to define or quantify, an approach based on evolutionary “milestones” can illuminate the underlying pattern. I propose that the robustness of this growth suggests a partly deterministic process that applies not only to Earth but potentially to the universe as a whole. This perspective also offers a novel solution to Fermi’s paradox: extraterrestrial civilizations may be at most as complex as we are and therefore have not yet developed interstellar communication. Finally, I explore future implications, in which human minds and technology increasingly merge, giving rise to new levels of complexity.

Introduction

The universe can be seen as a vast history of rising complexity. From the formation of the first atoms after the Big Bang, to the emergence of life, multicellular organisms, human culture, and now digital technologies, complexity appears to have increased without interruption. Yet, despite its centrality in fields such as Big History, evolutionary biology, and systems theory, complexity remains a concept that is difficult to define and even harder to quantify. Scholars have debated whether complexity is best understood in terms of information, entropy, or network dynamics, but no consensus has been reached.

In this article, I propose that—despite definitional challenges—the long-term trajectory of the universe can be characterized as a robust, exponential growth of complexity. I suggest that this trend is partly deterministic, resilient to catastrophic disruptions, and possibly universal. Building on this perspective, I offer a novel interpretation of Fermi’s paradox: if the growth of complexity is governed by a universal constant, then extraterrestrial civilizations are likely to be no more complex than we are today.

Evolution and Complexity Growth

Human evolutionary history can be understood as a sequence of qualitative leaps, each representing an increase in complexity. Following Richard Dawkins’ *Ancestor’s Tale* (2004), which identifies forty branching points in the evolutionary tree, we may view these milestones not simply as genealogical divisions but as transitions into

new levels of organization and function. Examples include the emergence of oxygen-breathing organisms, the first land animals, or mammals whose warm-bloodedness and lactation allowed greater ecological expansion and enhanced neural development. Each of these innovations opened novel evolutionary “playing fields,” niches that were previously inaccessible, and created opportunities for complexity to accumulate further.

Traditionally, evolutionary theory has emphasized natural selection as a process without inherent direction: natural selection of favorable traits which may cause a species to become larger or smaller, faster or slower, darker or lighter or more complex or simpler, depending on environmental pressures. In this view, complexity itself is not an inevitable outcome but a statistical effect. Stephen

Figure 1. Complexity as represented by Gould (1996)

Jay Gould (1996), for instance, argued that complexity evolves in a “drunkard’s walk” pattern: species wander randomly away from a minimum boundary of simplicity, and only over vast geological timescales does an apparent bias toward more complex organisms emerge (Figure 1 above). From this perspective, simplicity remains equally possible, and the rise of complex forms is partly a mirage of statistical variance.

Yet an alternative interpretation is possible. If the most complex organism at any given time gains novel capacities that allow it to expand into entirely new domains, then being “the most complex” is itself an evolutionary advantage. Higher complexity opens new strategies of survival, reproduction, and environmental mastery that simpler organisms cannot access. Humans illustrate this principle vividly: our unprecedented cognitive and cultural complexity has enabled us to dominate ecosystems, develop advanced technologies, and accelerate innovation beyond any other species. This resonates with Ray Kurzweil’s (2005) *Law of Accelerating Returns*: each breakthrough builds upon earlier complexity, enabling faster and more radical change. In this framework, evolution is not a random walk away from simplicity, but a compounding process in which complexity accelerates because complexity itself confers advantages.

The schematic overview (Figure 2) illustrates this concept. On the x-axis time is displayed, y-axis shows complexity. The different colors show selected paradigm shifts in mankind’s own history starting at the Big Bang, to the creation of life (green), multicellular life/Cambrian Explosion (beige), primates (pink), hominoids (orange), Homo sapiens (yellow) and culture in grey. Mankind’s path towards higher complexity is straight (on a log scale), others more random, like that of the horse with which we share a common ancestor a little over a hundred million years ago or like that of Neanderthals which branched off about

Figure 2. *Depiction of complexity growth of man’s evolution and that of some additional entities, conceptually*

400,000 years ago and went extinct roughly 30,000 years ago at which time they also displayed some cultural traits or that of an Iron atom which was created in the first collapsing stars and which remained the exact same ever since.

Exponential Complexity Growth

The increase of complexity across cosmic and biological history can be interpreted as an exponential process. Each rise in complexity not only represents a new organizational threshold but also accelerates the pace of subsequent change. The formation of atoms enabled the formation of molecules, which in turn enabled the emergence of cellular life—each stage occurring on shorter timescales than the previous. This cumulative acceleration reflects what Ray Kurzweil (2005) has termed the *Law of Accelerating Returns*: future developments proceed faster because they build upon an ever more complex foundation.

To approximate this pattern, I adopt a heuristic approach based on evolutionary and cultural “milestones.” While the selection of milestones is necessarily somewhat subjective, they serve as proxies for major leaps in complexity. Examples include the Big Bang (~13.8 billion years ago), the origin of life (~3.8 billion years ago), the Cambrian

Complexity Rate of Change

Landmark event	Years ago	Years to next event
Big Bang	13,800,000,000	3,100,000,000
Supernova/heavy elements	10,700,000,000	6,900,000,000
Origin of life	3,800,000,000	1,300,000,000
Oxygen use	2,500,000,000	1,300,000,000
Sexual reproduction	1,200,000,000	600,000,000
Multicellular organisms	600,000,000	235,000,000
Amphibians	365,000,000	150,000,000
Mammals	215,000,000	90,000,000
Placental mammal	125,000,000	62,000,000
Primates	63,000,000	23,000,000
Haplorhini	40,000,000	15,000,000
Apes	25,000,000	12,000,000
Hominoids	13,000,000	6,000,000
Hominina/Chimpansee	7,000,000	3,400,000
Australopithecus	3,600,000	1,100,000
Homo	2,500,000	700,000
Homo erectus	1,800,000	1,284,000
Homo antecessor	516,000	161,000
Homo heidelbergensis	355,000	160,000
Homo sapiens	195,000	145,000
Great Leap Forward	50,000	31,000
Agriculture	19,000	7,000
Cities	12,000	12,000

Figure 3. Logarithmic plot of complexity milestones. When plotted on a logarithmic timescale, the intervals between milestones shorten, revealing an exponential trajectory of complexity growth. This pattern remains visible despite catastrophic disruptions.

explosion of multicellularity (~540 million years ago), the emergence of primates, the appearance of *Homo sapiens* (~200,000 years ago), the rise of agriculture and culture (~10,000 years ago), and the digital revolution in recent decades. Plotting these events on a logarithmic scale shows that the intervals between successive milestones shorten in a manner consistent with exponential acceleration (Figure 3 above).

This approach does not provide a precise quantitative rate of complexity growth, since complexity itself remains difficult to measure. However, the temporal clustering of key events strongly suggests that the overall trajectory follows an exponential curve. Importantly, the apparent rate of acceleration has remained robust despite catastrophic events, such as mass extinctions or global conflicts. These disruptions may have shifted the particular pathways of life or civilization, but they did not alter the larger trajectory of complexity. On a logarithmic scale, they vanish into statistical noise, leaving the exponential curve untouched. This resilience suggests that complexity growth is not merely a contingent outcome but a persistent and deterministic trend.

A striking feature of exponential growth is its subjective illusion. When projected on a logarithmic scale, the curve appears to approach zero—implying that an ultimate singularity, a point of infinite complexity, is always near. Yet this is misleading: the graph has always seemed to suggest that the singularity was imminent, and it always will. What looks impressively steep in comparison with the past will appear sluggish compared with the future. The illusion of the “ever-near singularity” is itself a natural byproduct of exponential processes, not evidence of an approaching endpoint.

Thus, while the precise constant of complexity growth remains undefined, the exponential acceleration observed in natural and cultural history supports the hypothesis that complexity functions as a driving force in the universe. Each milestone both emerges from prior complexity and enables the next, reinforcing a trajectory that is robust, cumulative, and accelerating.

The Future of Complexity Growth and Fermi’s Paradox

If the universe can be described as a system trending toward higher entropy, then life and complexity represent the opposite trajectory: entities that maintain or decrease internal entropy by exporting it outward (*negentropy*, Schrödinger (1944)). From this perspective, complexity

is not random but directional, and if robust exponential growth applies universally, then it may also provide insight into one of the most enduring puzzles in astrobiology: Fermi’s paradox.

Fermi’s paradox asks why, given the vast number of stars and habitable planets in our galaxy, we see no evidence of extraterrestrial civilizations. Estimates suggest there may be over 100 billion planets in the Milky Way, of which perhaps 40 billion could be potentially habitable (Petigura, Howard, & Marcy, 2013). The apparent silence is therefore puzzling. Numerous hypotheses have been proposed, ranging from self-destruction of advanced species, to the rarity of complex life (*Rare Earth hypothesis*; Ward and Brownlee (2000)), to the possibility that civilizations deliberately avoid contact (“zoo hypothesis”). Webb (2015) catalogued seventy-five such explanations, underscoring the lack of consensus.

I propose a different solution: if complexity growth is universal, robust, and exponential, then any extraterrestrial civilization will, at most, be as complex as we are right now. In other words, the absence of evidence is not due to extinction, rarity, or deliberate concealment, but because other civilizations are simply synchronized with us in their developmental trajectory. They, like us, may only recently have begun looking beyond their home planet, and thus lack the means for interstellar communication or travel.

This hypothesis rests on two premises. First, the principle of uniformitarianism: the same natural laws that govern Earth govern the rest of the cosmos. If exponential complexity growth has shaped our history from the Big Bang to the present, it would operate elsewhere under similar conditions. Second, robustness: catastrophic events have proven irrelevant to the overall trajectory of complexity on Earth. Mass extinctions, asteroid impacts, and world wars altered the details of history but not its direction. On cosmological timescales they vanish as statistical noise, leaving the exponential rise of complexity unaffected. If this resilience is a universal property, then the timeline of complexity across habitable planets would converge on comparable stages, regardless of local disruptions.

The implication is profound: the “Great Silence” may not indicate that we are alone, but rather that the universe is filled with civilizations just as nascent, just as emergent, and just as constrained as we are. Fermi’s paradox then dissolves into an expectation of simultaneity. At this moment, we are unlikely to detect civilizations significantly more advanced than ourselves—not because they do not

exist, but because they cannot yet exist.

This perspective transforms Fermi's paradox from a question of absence into a question of timing. It predicts that interstellar contact, if it occurs, will arise only once multiple civilizations independently reach the technological threshold for communication or travel. Until then, the accelerating trajectory of complexity will unfold in parallel across many worlds, unseen but synchronously advancing.

Speculative Outlook: The Big Future of Complexity

While the preceding sections have argued that complexity growth is robust, exponential, and potentially universal, the future trajectory of this process necessarily enters the realm of speculation. Nonetheless, it is worth considering the possible directions that exponential complexity may take.

At present, humanity appears to stand on the threshold of a new qualitative leap: the integration of human cognition with advanced technologies. The rising computational power of machines and the global interconnection provided by the internet already suggest the early stages of a merging between biological and technological forms of complexity. If past patterns hold, such integration may represent not an endpoint but the foundation for the next, faster stage of development.

On a planetary scale, billions of interconnected human minds, amplified by artificial intelligence, could form a new level of collective organization—a planetary network of complexity that transcends individual cognition. This planetary entity may, in turn, eventually link with other civilizations across the galaxy, if and when they too reach comparable thresholds of complexity. In such a scenario, galactic-scale entities of complexity could emerge, pushing the trajectory of evolution beyond biological and cultural boundaries into genuinely cosmic domains.

Admittedly, such projections are speculative. They extend the logic of exponential complexity into uncharted territory, and as such they must be treated as thought experiments rather than predictions. Yet speculation has heuristic value: it underscores the continuity of the pattern, highlights the scale of possible futures, and invites reflection on the potential role of humanity in the larger cosmic process.

Adams and Laughlin (1997) have argued that the universe will inevitably approach a state of heat death, as all astrophysical structures decay over cosmological timescales. While their analysis emphasizes the ultimate

dominance of entropy, the framework of exponential complexity growth raises the speculative possibility that hyper-complex systems—if they continue to evolve—might one day operate on cosmological scales, perhaps delaying or counteracting this trajectory. Whether or not such possibilities are realized, the history of complexity invites us to see ourselves not as isolated observers, but as active participants in a universal process whose trajectory is accelerating into the future.

Conclusion

The history of the universe can be interpreted as a story of exponential complexity growth, from the first atoms and molecules to multicellular life, human cognition, and technological civilization. While complexity remains notoriously difficult to define and quantify, the heuristic use of evolutionary and cultural milestones demonstrates a consistent pattern: complexity has grown robustly and exponentially, with each step enabling faster and deeper transformations.

This trajectory appears resilient even in the face of catastrophic disruptions such as mass extinctions or global conflicts, suggesting that complexity growth functions as a persistent trend, perhaps even a universal law. On the scale of billions of years, such events are effectively invisible: they may alter the details of history, but not its direction.

If this robustness holds universally, then the absence of advanced extraterrestrial civilizations may not reflect their nonexistence but their simultaneity with us: they are at most as complex as we are today. This reinterpretation of Fermi's paradox reframes the silence of the cosmos as an artifact of timing, not emptiness.

Looking forward, humanity may stand on the cusp of new levels of complexity, driven by the integration of human and technological systems. Whether or not such hyper-complex entities eventually influence even cosmological processes, one conclusion remains clear: complexity has been, and will continue to be, the driving force of Big History.

Future research should therefore focus on developing more precise frameworks for defining and quantifying complexity, exploring its resilience across different domains, and testing whether the trajectory observed on Earth can be generalized across the universe. In doing so, we may not only better understand our own evolutionary past, but also glimpse the larger cosmic future of complexity itself.

References:

- Adams, F. C., & Laughlin, G. (1997). A dying universe: The long-term fate and evolution of astrophysical objects. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 69(2), 337–372. <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.69.337>
- Dawkins, R. (2004). *The ancestor's tale: A pilgrimage to the dawn of life*. Weidenfeld & Nicolson.
- Gould, S. J. (1996). *Full house: The spread of excellence from Plato to Darwin*. Harmony Books.
- Kurzweil, R. (2005). *The singularity is near: When humans transcend biology*. Penguin.
- Petigura, E. A., Howard, A. W., & Marcy, G. W. (2013). Prevalence of Earth-size planets orbiting Sun-like stars. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 110(48), 19273–19278. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1319909110>
- Schrödinger, E. (1967). *What is life? The physical aspect of the living cell and mind and matter* (Reprint of 1944 ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Ward, P. D., & Brownlee, D. (2000). *Rare earth: Why complex life is uncommon in the universe*. Springer.
- Webb, S. (2015). *If the universe is teeming with aliens... where is everybody? Seventy-five solutions to the Fermi paradox and the problem of extraterrestrial life* (2nd ed.). Springer.

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